

OPTIMISATION OF MEDIA REPORTING IN THE CONTEXT OF OPEN DATA DEVELOPMENT

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1. Introduction

The right measure of media reporting on sensitive issues related to national security would be the optimal amount of information to integrate the essential tension between two contradictory demands. In this case we are talking about the demand for openness, in other words, the demand to give access to information that is critical for citizens, or, probably the best description, information of public interest. On the other side is the demand for secrecy with regard to national security.

The content of the concept of public interest could be raised as a debatable question. However, it is unlikely that subtle differences in the perception of public interest would significantly erase the importance of factors such as truthfulness of information, relevance of information, clarity and coherence of reporting. Quoting McQuail (2015):

“...there is the idea of ‘public interest’ as in the chapter title, used widely and diversely, sometimes misused and escaping an agreed definition except in very general terms (as a notion of the welfare of the public or society as a whole). However, Jay Blumler did suggest (1998) a fairly clear view of what it would mean, in terms of three key features: it refers to a vision of what is good for the many as instituted by some form of legitimate democratic authority (as are certain other functions in society, such as government or the justice system) and having an element of public responsibility as a consequence. It is an idea that requires a long time span, which takes into account the long-term needs and effects, thus of future as well as present generations. In addition, the notion of a public interest has to recognize conflicts of interest and of perspective in implementation; it must permit compromise and adaptation to the realities of the time and place.”

McQuail sees media theory as a complex structure of socio-political and philosophical principles, which organises ideas on the relationship between the media and society. As one of the few theories, in his classification we find the normative media theory. It deals with the issue

of what the media should do rather than what they are really doing. Despite the fact that McQuail categorises theory in a few basic varieties, he adds that in reality there are no clean models; rather, what exists in a concrete society is a model combining theoretical elements and media types. He also believes that basic principles of media activity can be isolated as independence, diversity or pluralism, information quality and the preservation of social and cultural order. He warns that some of these principles are conflicting, but that one of the aims of regulation is the very management of tensions and settlement of conflicts (McQuail, 2005). The conflict in focus in this research is between secrecy and openness, which we see as something that the national security system is entitled to do vs. the demand of the public as part of the norm of a democratic society. But it is just one of the many characteristics of this specific relationship between the system and the media. As stated by authors Peter Gill and Mark Phythian (2018) in their book “Intelligence in an Insecure World”, a part of their relationship can also be marked by a combination of dependence, manipulation, support and praise. These appearances are also directly connected to the possible negation of basic principles like independence and information quality.

As a wide variety of problems in science, engineering etc. can be posed as optimisation problems (Jain et al., 1996), the goal of a formed model, and hopefully an optimisation algorithm in the future, is to calculate that right measure, naturally following the results from the conducted research process, and to optimise information. Secondly, an alternative to optimising every piece of information (in this research information equals sentence) is to optimise the whole media article by picking only sentences that fall in the range of calculated values that are determined as those that legitimise publishing based on the scope and goal of the research.

2. Methodology

The methodology used in this research is mostly based on Florian Kohlbacher design. Firstly, a theoretical analysis was conducted. Afterwards, in the second phase, results of the theoretical analysis were applied to a certain amount of units. When we speak about units we mean sentences from the chosen media article. In this particular research we examined 34 sentences. We use structure analysis, syntax analysis, grammatical analysis and narrative analysis.

An empirical analysis after the theoretical analysis filtered the applied theoretical results. That's how we obtained the matrix as the meeting point of theoretical terms and their empirical usage. By picking patterns, the table was created and it contains formulas expressing connections between both empirical and theoretical examined elements.

In the third phase of research, the analysis was done based on the produced table and the results were recorded. Considering the overall goal of the research, many more units have to be included in order to achieve a bigger number of representative examples.

3. Theme framework

A theme framework needs to be defined in order to create a scope for the researching of fundamental theoretical terms in information sciences. Fundamental theoretical terms, on the one hand, are relevance, informativeness and usefulness, and on the other hand, they are data

and information. The theme framework is related to the national security concept but in its specific non-military aspects, like the inner structural weakness of the system, the vulnerability of the institution, the vulnerability of the value system related to political stability, and social cohesion (Buzan, 1983). Together with the aforementioned points, we are including situations when hybrid threat activity, by applying combinations of tools, targets a state in the legal, diplomatic, information and political domains. Then we talk about each tool targeting one or multiple domains, or the interface between them, by creating or exploiting a vulnerability or taking advantage of an opportunity (Giannopoulos, 2021). We could put all of the definitions under the same umbrella of finding a balance between democratic standards and registering hybrid threats in timely manner.

4. Theoretical analysis

The general definition of information (GDI) is an operational standard that defines the information as an item that 1) is composed of one piece of data or more data that 2) is well composed and 3) has meaning.

By well-composed data, we mean data that are composed in accordance with the syntax of a certain system, whereby syntax is seen as a term in a broader sense than linguistics, which includes the determination of form, construction, composition and structure (Floridi, 2011). The fundamental nature of the data is where we see x different to y , where x and y are two uninterpreted variables, or in other words, the fundamental nature of data is exhibiting the anomaly (Floridi, 2009).

“The term ‘information’ is often used to represent a variety of things, events or expressions. In other words the term ‘information’ cannot be interpreted as the things, events or expressions themselves unless it is situated within a context and is understood meaningfully” (Ma, 2012). Considering that, the research is done in a specific context to examine theory. Therefore, its results are to be interpreted only as such.

Over time, relevance was explored in different directions, but it is possible to summarise it into four approaches to the nature of relevance. It was found that the following emerged: systemic, communicative, situational and psychological, and we can add to these a fifth or interactive framework based on a layered interaction model of information searching, where interactions include levels or layers. It is considered that there is not only one relevance but an interdependent system of relevances, which dynamically interact with each other within and between different layers or levels and adapt when necessary. A categorisation of the manifestation of relevance was proposed and it was cross-referenced with the system of relevance. It is considered that relevance has a set of general features that characterise its nature, which includes:

- a) relation
- b) intention
- c) context
- d) inference by involving an assessment of a relation, often an advanced assessment of the success or degree of enhancement of a particular relation, such as an assessment of some information sought in relation to a context-directed intention

e) interaction meaning an inference is achieved as a dynamic, interactive process in which interpretations of other features can change, depending on understanding (Saračević, 2006).

Following this, in this research we consider relevance as the element strongly related to the characteristic of data, of which the particular information consists in the specific context. We find it is an unchangeable characteristic in the perspective of time.

$$R = (is + pr) \times ST$$

where

R - relevance

ST - truthlikeness

is – average correctness of data

pr – average preciseness of data

Counting on the fact that average preciseness and average correctness are not changeable, the only change we could expect in this is that of truthlikeness. We didn't include in our work the concept of truth because we strongly believe that it would limit the scope of the research and its usefulness. But we use the term truthlikeness. It is a concept that we observe in the following framework.

As there might be a betweenness relationship amongst worlds, or even a fully-fledged distance metric, we can examine what is closer to the truth. The essence of the likeness approach is that the truthlikeness of a proposition is somehow dependent on the likeness between worlds. Graham discusses three main problems for any concrete proposal within the likeness approach:

- a) an account of likeness between states of affairs –what does this consist of and how can it be analysed or defined?
- b) the dependence of the truthlikeness of a proposition on the likeness of worlds in its range to the actual world: what is the correct function?
- c) “translation variance” or “framework dependence” of judgements of likeness and of truthlikeness (Oddie, 2016).

The truthfulness that is a changing measure on this scale is actually the degree of realism of a particular claim or information, its proximity to the real state of affairs. The problem is determining the proximity to truth/reality/information (Floridi, 2011).

Following what was mentioned earlier in the research, we concluded that truthlikeness for the purpose of this research is the proportion of verifiable data from the total number of data.

$$ST = \frac{PP}{UBP}$$

where

PP - number of verifiable data

UBP - total number of data

It is critically important to define criteria for the verification of data. It is strongly advised not to keep a fixed number but constantly update this list. For this research we started with kinds of self-evident criterias, such as the possibility of confirmation in transparent records, minutes, public reports, publicly verified documents, public registers, and transparent actions of the involved actors, such as direct tv interviews or any other similar direct source, five open sources that confirm information (today it is not applicable due to lots of web copying), basic observations, all depending on the data we want to verify. Criteria as not having numerus clausus need to be constantly updated. During the analysis we observed a few more. In the examples below we see that the author used a very general syntagm “Croatian citizens“:

Data 5 Croatian citizens have started thinking about banks and the banking system that can hide many secrets - verifiable

Data 6 Croatian citizens have started thinking that the president could lie and be connected to crime if he has an advisor who can lie and be connected to crime - verifiable

Data 7 Croatian citizens began to think of other things as well - verifiable

We don't know their age, region in Croatia, education, even the number of people, so we could apply very simple sociological research, take an undefined sample of Croatian citizens (as here) and try to include 1,000 people so the research could be considered legitimate and verify/not verify this data. We can see that different data can be an inspiration for the indefinite number of criteria.

Specific time of the data publishing also turned out to be crucial in defining the criteria for the verification. The examples shown here are from the time when the Croatian Act on the right of access to information (OG 25/13, 85/15, 69/22) didn't exist in the legal system. As Article 3. of the Act states “The objective of this Act is to enable and ensure the exercise of the right of access to information and the reuse of information, as granted by the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, to natural persons and legal entities, through openness and the publicity of the activity of public authority bodies.” Therefore, from the moment the Act is valid in the country, we have many more verifiable data.

5. Conclusion

The criteria for data verification strongly influence the calculation of relevance that is defined as an unchangeable characteristic of the information as regards the publishing time, but as we stated before, we expect changes in the research results, even changes in the model itself, due to environment changes.

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